

Monthly Investigations of Absorption Coefficient of Cosmic Ray Intensity in the Atmosphere

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Abstract: This research conducts monthly investigations into the absorption coefficient of cosmic rays within Earth's atmosphere. Cosmic rays, originating from various astrophysical sources as high-energy particles, propagate through the atmosphere and interact with air molecules, resulting in absorption and attenuation of their intensity. The absorption coefficient characterizes the rate at which the intensity of cosmic rays decreases with atmospheric depth or height. Observations were made to identify patterns and trends in cosmic ray absorption over monthly timescales. Linear regression analysis was performed over 12 months using cosmic ray intensity data and the mid-height of atmospheric layers. The average absorption coefficient, represented as μ_{av} is 1.3×10^{-3} . Notably, the absorption coefficient for February is significantly lower compared to other months, indicating reduced absorption within the atmosphere due to low solar activity. This phenomenon occurs because cosmic rays with higher energies are less affected by solar modulation. These findings provide valuable insights into the variability of cosmic ray interactions with the atmosphere and their broader implications in atmospheric physics, climate science, and space weather research. Future research endeavors should concentrate on refining atmospheric modeling techniques and incorporating additional observational data to enhance our understanding of cosmic rays' role in shaping Earth's climate and space weather.

Keywords: Cosmic ray, Absorption coefficient, Atmosphere, Extensive air shower, Earth's climate.

Introduction

Cosmic rays are high-energy particles originating from various astrophysical sources beyond the solar system (Gaisser *et al.*, 2016).

They consist mainly of protons, atomic nuclei, and electrons accelerated to relativistic speeds. The energy spectrum of cosmic rays spans a wide range, from MeV to EeV (Swordy,

2001). Cosmic rays lose energy as they interact with atmospheric nuclei through ionization, bremsstrahlung, and other energy loss mechanisms. These processes result in a decrease in the intensity of cosmic rays with increasing atmospheric depth (Capdevielle *et al.*, 1998). These findings provided valuable insights into the variability of cosmic ray interactions with the atmosphere and their broader implications in atmospheric physics, climate science, and space weather research.

When cosmic rays penetrate the Earth's atmosphere, they collide with atmospheric nuclei, initiating an extensive air shower (EAS), which is a cascade of secondary particles. These secondary particles comprise electrons, positrons, photons, muons, and neutrons, among others (Grieder, 2001).

As cosmic rays traverse the atmosphere, they interact with air molecules, resulting in absorption and attenuation of their intensity (Stanev, 2013). The absorption coefficient delineates the rate at which the intensity of cosmic rays diminishes with atmospheric depth or height (Dorman, 2004). Monthly variations in cosmic ray intensity and absorption coefficient can be influenced by factors such as solar activity, geomagnetic effects, atmospheric conditions (temperature, pressure, humidity), and seasonal changes

(Usoskin *et al.*, 2016). Monitoring the absorption coefficient of cosmic ray intensity on a monthly basis provides valuable insights into how solar activity affects cosmic ray penetration into the Earth's atmosphere. This information is crucial for understanding space weather phenomena and their potential impacts on satellite operations, communication systems, and astronaut safety (Guzik *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, monthly variations in the absorption coefficient of cosmic ray intensity can help researchers investigate potential correlations between cosmic ray flux and cloud cover variations on Earth (Svensmark *et al.*, 2007).

The Earth's atmosphere is composed of several layers, each with distinct characteristics that influence the absorption of cosmic ray intensity. Understanding the depth of these atmospheric layers and their interaction with cosmic rays is essential for studying cosmic ray modulation and its impact on Earth's environment" (Dorman, 2004). Studies have investigated the origin and acceleration mechanisms of cosmic rays, with supernova remnants and active galactic nuclei identified as primary sources (Gaisser *et al.*, 1998).

In discussing the interaction of cosmic rays with the atmosphere, Dorman (2004)

concluded that the atmosphere acts as a shield, absorbing and attenuating cosmic ray flux, with absorption increasing with atmospheric depth and density. Studies have documented monthly variations in cosmic ray intensity, which are influenced by solar activity, geomagnetic effects, and atmospheric conditions (Bieber and Evenson, 2000). Belov *et al.* (2001) revealed that the absorption of cosmic rays in the atmosphere varies with altitude, with greater absorption occurring in denser atmospheric layers such as the troposphere.

Also, in investigating the atmospheric absorption effect on cosmic ray measurement for high altitude balloon flight, He *et al.* (2015) concluded that the extent of absorption depends on the energy of the cosmic rays and density of atmospheric constituents. Research has investigated correlations between cosmic ray flux and cloud cover variations, although the causal relationship remains debated (Svensmark and Friis-Christensen, 1997).

While there is increasing interest in comprehending the potential connections between cosmic rays and climate variability, current research frequently lacks integration with atmospheric absorption studies. This investigation aims to fill this void by examining the monthly variations in

absorption coefficients, thereby enhancing our understanding of the intricate interactions between cosmic rays and Earth's climate system.

Materials and Methods

Sources of Data

Mexico City Observatory (<http://132.248.105.25/index.php>) as a Neutron monitor network is the source of cosmic ray intensity data. Alan Buis/NASA's Global Climate Change (climate.nasa.gov) provided the heights of Atmospheric layers.

Method of Data Analysis

The cosmic ray intensity data were collected for a period of twelve (12) months. Linear regression analysis was carried out for each month using the cosmic ray intensity (I) and the mid-height (h) of the atmospheric layers (Troposphere, Stratosphere, Mesosphere and Thermosphere). This gave us a straight line equation of the form:

$$\ln I_0 = \mu h + \ln I \quad (1)$$

as the intercept, $\ln I$ depicts the amount that remained; which help to determine the absorption level of cosmic ray (CR) for each month.

μ is the value of the absorption coefficient of CR in the atmosphere. Hence, we made our

observations and identified patterns and trends in cosmic ray absorption over monthly timescales

Results and Discussion

Results

Table 1 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of January, 2022

Month of January (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	138125191	18.7437	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	138079932	18.7433	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	138343269	18.7452	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	197034032	19.0989	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 1 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of January, 2022

Table 2 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of February, 2022

Month of February (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	137838674	18.7416	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	137956844	18.7425	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	137839970	18.7416	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	137740485	18.7409	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 2 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of February, 2022

Table 3 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of March, 2022

Month of March (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	137874207	18.7419	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	137733647	18.7408	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	137441303	18.7387	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	197292222	19.1002	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 3 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of March, 2022

Table 4 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of April, 2022

Month of April (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	137846609	18.7417	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	138093840	18.7434	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	138501171	18.7464	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	175714359	18.9844	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 4 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of April, 2022

Table 5 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of May, 2022

Month of May (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	137004170	18.7355	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	137244452	18.7373	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	136346026	18.7307	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	194804747	19.0875	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 5 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of May, 2022

Table 6 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of June, 2022

Month of June (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	136437039	18.7314	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	137363976	18.7381	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	133727764	18.7113	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	173138872	18.9696	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 6 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of June, 2022

Table 7 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of July, 2022

Month of July (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	135920935	18.7276	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	135385995	18.7236	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	134405910	18.7164	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	188934599	19.0569	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 7 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of July, 2022

Table 8 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of August, 2022

Month of August (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	134470140	18.7169	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	133405479	18.7089	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	133828071	18.7121	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	189893514	19.0620	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 8 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of August, 2022

Table 9 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of September, 2022

Month of September (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	134123039	18.7143	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	135798716	18.7267	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	134139468	18.7144	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	171213980	18.9584	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 9 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of September, 2022

Table 10 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of October, 2022

Month of October (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	134152832	18.7145	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	136714027	18.7334	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	134551111	18.7175	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	192336729	19.0748	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 10 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of October, 2022

Table 11 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of November, 2022

Month of November (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	135605712	18.7253	0 – 12 (Troposphere)	6.00
Week 2	135204123	18.7223	12 – 50 (Stratosphere)	31.00
Week 3	135152377	18.7219	50 – 80 (Mesosphere)	65.00
Week 4	171976398	18.9629	80 – 700 (Thermosphere)	239.00

Figure 11 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of November, 2022

Table 12 Weekly investigations of CR Absorption within the atmospheric layers for the month of December, 2022

Month of December (2022)	CR Intensity, I_0	$\ln I_0$	Range of Heights of Atmospheric Layers (km)	Mid-Height (h) of the Atmospheric Layers (km)
Week 1	133939746	18.7129	0 – 12	6.00 (Troposphere)
Week 2	134682946	18.7184	12 – 50	31.00 (Stratosphere)
Week 3	134420161	18.7165	50 – 80	65.00 (Mesosphere)
Week 4	189201414	19.0583	80 – 700	239.00 (Thermosphere)

Figure 12 Graph of I_0 against h for the month of December, 2022

Table 13 Monthly values of absorption coefficients of CR within the atmosphere, μ

Month	Absorption Coefficient of CR within the Atmosphere, μ
January	0.0016
February	- 0.000005
March	0.0017
April	0.0011
May	0.0016
June	0.0011
July	0.0015
August	0.0016
September	0.0011
October	0.0016
November	0.0011
December	0.0016
μ_{total}	0.015595

Discussion

The average value of the absorption coefficient, μ_{av} is thus:

$$\mu_{av} = \frac{\mu_{total}}{12} = \frac{0.015595}{12} = 1.3 \times 10^{-3} \quad (1)$$

Suppose a height of an absorber (layer of atmosphere) reduces the cosmic ray intensity I by an amount dI , then we obtained: $\frac{dI}{dh} \propto I$

This implies: $\frac{dI}{dh} = -\mu I$ Or $\frac{dI}{I} = -\mu dh$ (2)

where μ is the absorption coefficient. Taking integral of both sides, we obtained:

$$\int_0^I \frac{dI}{I} = \int_0^h -\mu dh \quad (3)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{I}{I_0}\right) = -\mu \int_0^h dh \quad (4)$$

$$I = I_0 e^{-\mu h} \quad (5)$$

I_0 is the initial value of CR intensity, I is the amount of CR intensity that remained after absorption, $\mu = 1.3 \times 10^{-3}$ is the average value of the absorption coefficient of CR in the atmosphere. Linearizing equation (1), we obtained:

$$\ln I = -\mu h + \ln I_0 \quad (6)$$

$$\ln I_0 = \mu h + \ln I \quad (7)$$

$$\therefore \ln I_0 = (1.3 \times 10^{-3})h + \ln I \quad (8)$$

$\ln I$ being the intercept of the monthly graphs (Fig. 1 to Fig. 12) depicts the amount that remained; which help to determine the absorption level of CR for each month. Upon careful examination of the regression equation derived from the graph plotted for each month, the slope represents the value of the absorption coefficient, denoted as μ . These observed monthly variations in the absorption coefficient of cosmic ray intensity hold significant implications for atmospheric

physics, climate variability, and space weather forecasting.

Based on the data presented in Table 13, it is evident that the absorption coefficient for the month of February is notably lower in comparison to the values recorded for other months. This observed decrease in February's absorption coefficient could potentially be attributed to diminished solar activity. Lower solar activity levels can lead to reduced modulation of cosmic rays by the solar wind and heliospheric magnetic field. As noted by Bieber and Evenson (2000), "During periods of low solar activity, cosmic rays exhibit higher energies and are consequently less influenced by solar modulation, resulting in decreased absorption within the atmosphere."

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research has yielded significant insights into the monthly fluctuations of the absorption coefficient of cosmic rays within Earth's atmosphere through a rigorous statistical analysis. These findings contribute substantively to the progression of atmospheric physics, climate science, and space weather research. Moving forward, it is recommended that future investigations concentrate on refining atmospheric modeling techniques,

incorporating supplementary observational data, and exploring long-term trends in cosmic ray absorption. Such endeavors will enhance our comprehension of the intricate role cosmic rays play in shaping Earth's climate and space weather phenomena.

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